

**DYNAMICS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE NUMBER OF ATMS AND
COMMERCIAL BANK BRANCHES IN MIDDLE, LOWER MIDDLE, AND UPPER MIDDLE
INCOME COUNTRIES**

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable economic development and decent welfare of the population require continuous and targeted movement of the required volume of financial resources. To achieve such movement, special attention is paid to the proper functioning of the banking system, the development of its institutional structure, and a network of tools for ensuring banking activities. Among such tools, the following should be highlighted: the number of ATMs and commercial bank branches. These components can also reflect the development of innovative solutions in the context of the formation of a digital economy, taking into account the factor of economic development of an individual country or group of countries. Based on this, the paper examines the dynamics of the relationship between the number of ATMs and commercial bank branches in countries with average, lower average and higher average income. The course of the study and its results are presented in the form of various graphs and diagrams. This helps to understand the results obtained and assess their possibility of practical use.

Keywords: Dynamics, ATMs, Banking, Bank branches, Comparative analysis, Innovative solutions, Digital economy.

Introduction

Banks play an important role in the economic development and well-being of both individual business entities and the state as a whole, the citizens of the country [1], [2]. This is due to the ability to accumulate and redistribute financial resources between various economic agents, to act as an intermediary for the population in the financial services market in ensuring their well-being [3]-[10]. Banking services and banking instruments can also be used to properly ensure the savings of the population accumulate the necessary resources or attract them in cases of need and in sufficient volume.

Institutionally, to ensure the functioning of the banking system and the provision of various services, special attention should be paid to the number of commercial bank branches and the number of ATMs [11], [12]. In particular, the number of ATMs is a reflection of the development of innovative solutions in the banking sector in the context of the formation and development of the digital economy. Also important is the mutual analysis between the dynamics of the number of commercial bank branches and ATMs, which allows us to determine the direction of development of banking services. For these purposes, various methods and approaches can be used, both classical [13]-[21] and special ones, allowing us to better understand the essence of the processes under consideration [22]-[30].

When considering the mutual dynamics of the number of commercial bank branches and ATMs, it is advisable to conduct a comparative analysis. Such an analysis can be conducted in the context of individual countries or their groups. Among such groups of countries, it is necessary to highlight countries with average, below average and above average income. Such consideration allows us to understand the general trends in the development of the banking sector of the economy for countries of a certain type, in particular from the point of view of the income received. This, in turn, reflects the level of economic development of the country and allows us to talk about trends in the number of commercial bank branches and the number of ATMs depending on the level of

economic development. Various special methods and approaches are also used for such analysis [31]-[41].

Thus, the main objective of this study is to analyze the dynamics of the relationship between the number of ATMs and commercial branches of banks in countries with average, lower average and higher average income. In order to achieve this goal, the work includes: a brief analysis of related works; consideration of the dynamics of the number of ATMs and commercial branches of banks; and a corresponding comparative analysis.

Related work

Given the purpose of this study, attention should be paid to various publications on the issue under consideration. Here, both theoretical and practical studies based on statistical analysis should be noted. Below, some examples of such works are considered, allowing a better understanding of the problematic of such studies.

P. Varma, S. Nijjer, K. Sood, S. Grima and R. Rupeika-Apoga analyze the impact of financial technologies on the development of the banking sector in their study [42]. The work notes that a violation in the use of such technologies can lead to a significant change in banking services and, as a result, to risk. At the same time, the authors show that fintech has enormous potential for growth and influence on the banking industry [42]. At the same time, the use of new technologies and cooperation between fintech companies and banks can improve system-wide financial stability [42]. This confirms the feasibility of conducting a corresponding analysis within the framework of the stated objectives of the study.

H. M. Alzoubi and T. M. Ghazal examine the impact of electronic payments on sales growth using data from the banking industry [43]. The study examines data from the UAE banking system and is based on quantitative data analysis. Particular attention is also paid to the existing ATM system, which allows for easy access to financial resources.

The role of the introduction of modern financial technologies in ensuring the competitiveness and efficiency of banks is considered in the work of P. Dwivedi, J. I. Alabdooli and R. Dwivedi [44]. The study was conducted on the basis of a survey of 76 banking professionals and managers from Dubai (UAE) [44]. The results of the work show that the introduction of modern technologies and innovations has a significant impact on the competitiveness and competitiveness results in the productivity of the banking industry in the UAE. Therefore, it is important to develop an adequate network of ATMs and commercial bank branches. This is also based on the fact that the UAE banking industry serves almost 200 nationalities.

A. S. Villar and N. Khan study the impact of robotic process automation on the development of banking activities [45]. This analysis is conducted using Deutsche Bank as an example. The work notes that robotic process automation ensures the development of several generations of bots. At the same time, such automation is most effective for repetitive work with low added value. This leads, in particular, to the expansion of the ATM network. Ultimately, the banking industry is transformed, making basic financial transactions exponentially more efficient [45].

In this regard, C. M. A. Maity and T. N. Sahu in their work examine the relationship between the expansion of bank branches and financial inclusion [46]. Such an analysis is conducted using the example of some commercial banks in India. The authors note that banks play a more important role in the growth and development of the economy by expanding their branches. Moreover, access to finance is necessary not only to maintain and improve the social and economic status of a person, but is also necessary to meet all needs [46]. For the purposes of the study, a regression model is used, where one of the variables reflects the dynamics of bank branches, including external ATMs. It is also emphasized that bank branches are the main interface between government and official deposit and credit accounts [46]. Therefore, it is also important to have some generalizations for a group of countries.

The study by T. B. Amene and D. B. Buta focused on the factors influencing customer satisfaction with ATM usage [47]. The study used Ethiopian banks as the basis for the analysis. The

data was collected using semi-structured questionnaires. Descriptive statistical analysis was applied to the data. It was found that time saving is the main reason for using ATM services [47]. At the same time, the results of multiple regression showed that responsiveness, efficiency, appearance, reliability and convenience of the ATM have a significant and positive impact on customer satisfaction [47].

G. N. Al-Eitan, B. Al-Own, and T. Bani-Khalid examine the impact of financial inclusion on the profitability of Jordanian commercial banks [48]. The paper examined the data of 13 Jordanian banks from 2009 to 2019. The study used fixed effects in relation to the panel data regression model [48]. It was shown that the number of branches and ATMs did not have a significant impact on bank profitability. Overall, both leverage and bank size were the two main determinants of commercial bank profitability in Jordan [48].

Y. C. Pamungkas and A. N. Fajar consider the possibility of improving business processes when implementing a network communication device to support online banking branches and ATMs [49]. This approach provides a system that will help in optimizing business processes, ensuring that the internal and external customers of the organization receive the best result [49]. For this, an analysis of the activities in each business process is carried out, where each of these activities has different characteristics. The authors state that based on the results of the evaluation and modeling, further research can use the evaluation results as a reference in preparing the analysis and developing software applications for the operation of the ATM network [49].

Thus, the analysis of the relevant literature showed the importance of the research problem under consideration. Various methods can be used here to study the dynamics of the number of ATMs and bank branches. However, it is important to conduct a mutual analysis of such dynamics, which allows us to reveal the existing conditions for the growth and development of banking activities and the economy as a whole. At the same time, to conduct the appropriate analysis, certain groups of countries should be considered, which allows us to make the necessary generalizations and conclusions. Based on this, among such groups, countries with lower middle income, middle income and upper middle income are considered.

Dynamics of the number of ATMs and bank branches in the considered research sample

This section examines the dynamics of the number of ATMs (in the period from 2004 to 2021) and bank branches (in the period from 2004 to 2023) per 100,000 adult population for countries with lower middle income, middle income and upper middle income. The dynamics of the corresponding data are presented in Fig. 1 – Fig. 3 (from the website <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator>).

Figure 1: Dynamics of the number of ATMs and bank branches in the group of countries with lower middle income

In Fig. 1 – Fig. 3 the left scale displays the values of the number of bank branches, the right scale displays the values of the number of ATMs. The black line displays the dynamics of the number of bank branches, the green line displays the dynamics of the number of ATMs.

The figures also show: absolute values of the number of ATMs and bank branches – Fig. 1a, Fig. 2a, Fig. 3a and relative values of the corresponding data – Fig. 1b, Fig. 2b and Fig. 3b. Relative

values are presented as the ratio of such data to the dynamics of the number of ATMs and bank branches in all countries of the world. Then relative data greater than 1 indicate the prevalence of the corresponding global data values, otherwise – the prevalence of such values in the context of individual data groups (for countries with lower middle income, middle income or upper middle income).

Fig. 1 shows the dynamics of the number of ATMs and bank branches in the group of countries with lower middle income. It should be noted that the dynamics of the absolute values of the number of ATMs and bank branches for countries with lower middle income is increasing (Fig. 1a). At the same time, the relative dynamics of such data is decreasing (Fig. 1b), although at the beginning of the study period, an increase in such dynamics is observed. The decreasing relative dynamics of the studied data indicates that in the group of countries with lower middle income, the absolute increase in the number of ATMs and bank branches is lower in comparison with all other countries. Therefore, over the entire studied data interval, it should be noted that the data for the whole world prevails over the corresponding data for countries with lower middle income (Fig. 1b).

Fig. 2 shows the dynamics of the number of ATMs and bank branches in the group of countries with middle income.

Figure 2: Dynamics of the number of ATMs and bank branches in the group of countries with middle income

As in the previous case, the absolute dynamics of the number of ATMs and bank branches in the group of countries with middle income is increasing (Fig. 2a), and the relative dynamics are decreasing (Fig. 2b). However, this dynamics differs from the dynamics for lower middle income countries (Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b). At the same time, the absolute values of the number of ATMs and bank branches in middle income countries are higher than in lower middle income countries. At the same time, the relative values of the number of ATMs and bank branches in middle income countries are lower than in lower middle income countries. Thus, we can say that the absolute increase in the number of ATMs and bank branches in middle income countries is higher than in lower middle income countries. Nevertheless, over the entire studied data interval, it should be noted that the data for the whole world prevails over the corresponding data for middle income countries.

Fig. 3 shows the dynamics of the number of ATMs and bank branches in the group of countries with upper middle income.

The dynamics of absolute and relative values of the number of ATMs and bank branches in the group of countries with upper middle income differs radically from the corresponding dynamics for countries with lower middle income and middle income. First of all, it should be noted that the absolute dynamics of the number of bank branches in the group of countries with upper middle income initially has an increasing trend, and in the last third of the studied period, a decreasing trend. Accordingly, the relative dynamics of the number of bank branches initially has a decreasing trend, and then increases. This indicates a possible paradigm shift in the development of the network,

primarily bank branches. And this should be taken into account when determining the strategy for the development of banking. At the same time, for many time intervals, the relative values of the studied data for countries with upper middle income are higher than for the data for the whole world. Consequently, countries with upper middle income determine the world trends in the values of the number of ATMs and bank branches.

Figure 3: Dynamics of the number of ATMs and bank branches in the group of countries with upper middle income

For a more in-depth analysis, we will also consider the comparative dynamics between the number of ATMs and bank branches across the groups of countries studied, respectively.

Comparative assessment of the mutual dynamics of the studied data

To conduct a comparative analysis between the studied data, the wavelet coherence method is used. This approach is widely used in the study of the corresponding data [31]-[35].

Fig. 4 presents estimates of wavelet coherence between the number of ATMs and bank branches for countries with lower middle income (for absolute and relative data values, respectively).

Figure 4: Wavelet coherence estimates between the number of ATMs and bank branches for countries with lower middle income

Based on the data in Fig. 4, it should be noted that there is different consistency between the data under study. However, such consistency is not absolute. This is explained by both the dynamics of the banking sector development in countries with lower middle income, and the use of certain strategies for such development, and the insufficiency of the base for the corresponding growth.

Fig. 5 presents estimates of wavelet coherence between the number of ATMs and bank branches for countries with middle income.

Here, it is also worth noting the different consistency between the data under study. At the same time, such consistency is not absolute, primarily from the point of view of absolute data. At the

same time, for relative data, such consistency is much higher. This is explained by the importance of data on countries with middle income in the overall dynamics of the number of ATMs and bank branches in general with existing global trends.

Figure 5: Wavelet coherence estimates between the number of ATMs and bank branches for countries with middle income

Fig. 6 presents estimates of wavelet coherence between the number of ATMs and bank branches for countries with upper middle income.

Figure 6: Wavelet coherence estimates between the number of ATMs and bank branches for countries with upper middle income

The data presented in Fig. 6 also have different dynamics of the corresponding consistency. This can be explained by the importance of the group of countries with upper middle income in the general world dynamics of the studied data, as well as the use of special strategies for the development of banking in countries with upper middle income. Finally, it should be noted that it is advisable to use wavelet coherence estimates for the corresponding analysis.

Conclusion

The paper examines some issues of the functioning of the banking sector of the economy from the point of view of individual groups of countries. For this purpose, the relationship between the number of ATMs and commercial branches of banks in countries with lower middle income, middle

income and upper middle income is studied. In order to substantiate certain areas of research, a brief analysis of related works on the topic under consideration is carried out. An analysis of the absolute values of the number of ATMs and commercial branches of banks is also carried out. The relative dynamics of the data is considered, which is reduced to the corresponding data in general for all countries.

For a more in-depth analysis, the wavelet coherence method is used, which allows for a better understanding of the dynamics of the data sets under consideration. It is noted that the results obtained can be used for decision-making for the development of banking.

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